

A REVIEW ON CURCUMIN LOADED CHITOSAN-BASED HYDROGELS FOR ACNE TREATMENT FORMULATION PARAMETERS IMPACTING ANTI-MICROBIAL RELEASE AND EFFICACY

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INTRODUCTION

Despite significant progress in modern allopathic treatments and healthcare infrastructure in developing countries, about 60% of the global population still depends on plant-based remedies for managing illnesses. Furthermore, nearly 75% of people worldwide continue to practice traditional medicinal systems, such as Ayurveda and Unani. Mango ginger (*Curcuma amada*), a rhizomatous aromatic herb, is a member of the Zingiberaceae family and is widely recognized for its therapeutic potential.^[1] The discovery of curcumin began around 200 years ago when Vogel and Pelletier revealed the successful separation of curcumin. This yellow pigment made from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, often known as turmeric, is called curcumin.^[2] Turmeric is obtained from *Curcuma longa* L., a perennial herbaceous species distinguished by its tuberous roots, yellow flowers, and broad leaves. This plant, a member

of the Zingiberaceae family, predominantly grows in tropical regions.^[3] *Curcuma longa* has long been utilized as a natural colorant, flavouring, and medicinal herb, particularly in Asian countries. Indian traditional medicine, culinary, and cosmetic items all make extensive use of it. Curcumin, the primary bioactive component, has a variety of pharmacological effects, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, chemopreventive, and possibly enhanced chemotherapeutic efficacy.^[4] Since ancient times, humans have relied on herbs and natural products to treat a variety of ailments. The Indian subcontinent, known for its rich biodiversity, hosts numerous aromatic and medicinal plants. Prior to their adoption as primary

therapeutic agents, it is crucial to rigorously evaluate and standardize Unani and Ayurvedic medicines to ensure their efficacy, safety, and quality. Across cultures, plant-based therapies remain integral to healthcare, with many countries allocating 40% to 50% of their health budgets to the development of new herbal drugs. Herbal medicines are generally perceived as beneficial to health with minimal risk of adverse effects.^[5]

A naturally occurring polyphenol called curcumin is taken from the rhizome of the perennial herb *Curcuma longa*. Because of its distinct flavour, it is frequently added to meals as a natural flavouring. Curcumin is a fat-soluble pigment that changes colour in response to pH: it appears yellow in neutral or acidic settings and reddish-brown in alkaline ones.

An efficient method for administering therapeutic drugs both locally and systemically is transdermal medication delivery. The stratum corneum, the skin's outermost layer, in particular, functions as a major barrier that restricts the penetration and absorption of drugs.^[6]

To achieve effective therapeutic outcomes, it is essential to enhance the saturation and absorption of drugs through the skin. A key strategy to overcome the barrier posed by the skin is the careful selection of penetration enhancers. These substances make it easier for drugs to penetrate the skin by momentarily altering its ordered structure. The best penetration enhancers should be non-irritating, non-allergic, non-toxic, and compatible with both medications and excipients. However, many commonly used chemical enhancers may cause both local and systemic side effects, highlighting the need to explore safer, effective, and cost-efficient alternatives.^[7]

In the realm of wound care, particularly for infected wounds, research has increasingly focused on developing dressings that incorporate antimicrobial agents. Because they imitate the extracellular matrix and produce a moist environment that is essential for wound healing, hydrogels have attracted a lot of attention. These hydrogels promote cell migration and proliferation, shield newly created cells from external harm, and reduce the creation of scars. Due to its biocompatibility and biodegradability, gelatin is one of the hydrogel materials most frequently used for wound healing.

Although topical antimicrobials are essential for treating infected wounds, their overuse has led to bacterial resistance and the establishment of resistant strains despite their effectiveness. Finding safer antimicrobial drugs with fewer adverse effects is therefore essential. Compared

to conventional antibiotics, curcumin, a natural substance, has a better safety profile, fewer side effects, and possible antibacterial action. Its antioxidant qualities and structural features significantly limit bacterial growth. Nevertheless, curcumin's poor water solubility, short half-life, and rapid metabolism limit its clinical application, especially for chronic infected wounds.

To overcome these difficulties, a curcumin-loaded nanocomposite hydrogel dressing (GelMA/AHA-Gel@Cur) was created. This dressing helps bacterially infected wounds recover by combining antibacterial action with prolonged medication release. Based on a modified gelatin matrix (GelMA/AHA), the hydrogel offers improved therapeutic potential for wound healing by utilizing the synergistic advantages of dextran and gelatin nanoparticles.^[8]

Gel@Cur nanoparticles were created when van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions caused gelatin molecules to cluster and encapsulate curcumin. These nanoparticles were encapsulated into the GelMA hydrogel network using aldehyde-modified hyaluronic acid (AHA) by Schiff base reactions. Methacrylated gelatin (GelMA) and AHA were crosslinked simultaneously using radical polymerization and Schiff base chemistry to create a composite hydrogel network.^[9]

Curcumin is a multifunctional molecule capable of interacting with multiple target sites. It demonstrates a variety of biological actions as a polyphenolic nutraceutical, such as antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and wound-healing properties.^[10]

The main phytochemical components of *Curcuma longa* L.'s rhizome include curcumin, often referred to as diferuloylmethane, and other curcuminoids. Curcumin's chemical structure is 1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione, commonly referred to as turmeric and belonging to the Zingiberaceae family.^[11]

Curcumin incorporated into a collagen matrix (CICM) was evaluated in vitro using the lipid peroxidation assay, demonstrating curcumin's strong antioxidant activity against peroxy-radicals. In vivo, transdermal application of curcumin on excision wounds in rats effectively mitigated H₂O₂-induced damage to keratinocytes and fibroblasts.^[12]

For centuries, turmeric has been used extensively throughout Asia as a spice, food preservative, and traditional treatment for a number of serious and minor illnesses. Its notable

medicinal properties are well-documented in ancient Indian texts. These therapeutic attributes have prompted extensive research focused on curcumin, the primary active compound in turmeric, which demonstrates a broad spectrum of beneficial biological activities.^[13]

Morphological characterization remains a valuable method alongside molecular techniques due to its reliability, ease of identification, and minimal resource requirements for assessing stable traits unaffected by environmental factors. In India, the Protection of Plant Varieties and Farmers' Rights Act (2001) mandates the evaluation of distinctness, uniformity, and stability (DUS) for existing, farmer-developed, and new plant varieties, recommending registration based on at least one novel characteristic. This framework facilitates the classification of morphological traits into both quantitative and qualitative categories (PPV & FRA, 2009). Accordingly, this study aimed to characterize 15 turmeric genotypes by assessing various morphological and rhizome traits in accordance with DUS guidelines.^[14]

Due to its advantageous characteristics and adaptable preparation techniques in pharmaceutical and medical applications, there is an increasing interest in the creation of medically relevant hydrogels. Research has focused on both natural and synthetic polymers in hydrogel formulation. Among these, chitosan, a natural cationic copolymer, has garnered significant attention for hydrogel construction. Its hydrophilic nature and enzymatic degradability in the human body confer biocompatibility and biodegradability, two essential attributes for biomedical devices. Chitosan-based hydrogels show promising potential as scaffolds for tissue engineering and facilitating tissue repair.^[15]

HISTORY

Curcumin was originally described by Vogel and Pelletier approximately 200 years ago as the compound responsible for turmeric's distinctive yellow color. It was first isolated in pure form by Vogel Jr. in 1842. By the mid-20th century, curcumin had been recognized for its biological activity, particularly its antibacterial effects against pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *Trichophyton* species.^[16]

In addition to curcumin, Srinivasan found curcuminoids in turmeric by chromatographic analysis in 1953. In vitro and in vivo studies have demonstrated curcumin's anticancer effects in addition to its cholesterol-lowering, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. Additionally, curcumin's efficacy and safety have been shown by human clinical

studies. Curcumin is "generally recognized as safe" (GRAS) according to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA).^[17]

Curcumin was first identified almost 200 years ago when Vogel and Pelletier separated curcumin, a yellow pigment, from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, also known as turmeric. This substance was first identified as a mixture of resin and turmeric oil. In 1842, Vogel Jr. obtained a pure form of curcumin, but he did not disclose its molecular makeup. Several chemists proposed potential curcumin structures during the following decades. It wasn't until 1910 that Milobedzka and Lampe identified the chemical structure of 1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione-1,7-bis (4-hydroxy-3 methoxyphenyl) -(1E,6E) as diferuloylmethane.^[18]

Since ancient times, plants have served as a primary source of medicinal compounds. In Asian countries, turmeric has long been used as a flavour, medicinal herb, and colouring. Turmeric's characteristic yellow hue is caused by curcumin, which was first identified almost 200 years ago. Diferuloylmethane was identified as its chemical structure in 1910. Turmeric's anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, anticancer, and antioxidant properties are attributed to its primary bioactive polyphenol, curcumin.

To mediate these effects, a variety of growth factors, transcription factors, inflammatory cytokines, protein kinases, and enzymes are controlled. The purpose of this review is to demonstrate curcumin's pharmacological properties and therapeutic potential for improving oral health.^[19]

The use of turmeric (curcumin) can be traced back to the *Atharva Veda* (1000–1500 BC), a sacred Hindu text, where it is referred to as 'Haldi' or 'Haridra'. Additionally, the ancient Indian medicinal system of Ayurveda, which dates back approximately 5000 years, extensively documents the therapeutic applications of turmeric. Ethnobotanical evidence supports the longstanding use of turmeric in India, often associated with the worship of the 'Shakti' or Mother Goddess. Historical records indicate that turmeric was introduced to China around 700 AD, as noted by Marco Polo (1280). Furthermore, Purse glove et al. (1981) suggested a Malaya–Polynesian origin for turmeric, linking its use in Madagascar to Pre-Aryan Indian cultures.

The goal of this review is to provide a succinct overview of current studies on the medicinal potential of curcumin and its derivatives. Curcumin's antibacterial, anticancer, anti-

Alzheimer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral activities against coronavirus, and neuroprotective qualities are highlighted due to the vast amount of data. Several clinical trials are currently underway, which are expected to further elucidate the clinical applications and efficacy of curcumin in the coming years.^[20]

SKIN: THE FIRST DEFENSE LINE As the largest and most visible organ in the body, the skin protects against external threats including microbial invasion and stops internal fluid loss. The epidermis, which is its outermost layer, serves as a barrier of defense. This layer is made up of many cell strata, the outermost of which constantly sheds dead cells. This protective ability is mostly dependent on the immune system of the skin. Langerhans cells in the epidermis identify foreign substances and initiate immunological responses. The skin also contains additional immune cells that aid in preventing infections from entering, such as T cells and macrophages.^[8]

In brief, the skin's layered structure works together effectively to provide a strong initial barrier against external threats, maintaining the body's health and integrity. Due to its extensive surface area, the skin offers significant potential for drug administration. It can be used for topical, dermal, or transdermal delivery methods. Topical delivery targets the drug to remain on the skin's surface layers, dermal delivery allows the medication to reach the deeper dermis, while transdermal delivery enables drugs to pass through the skin into systemic circulation.^[21]

Figure No 1: Structural and Immunological Components of the Skin.

TYPES OF SKIN INFECTIONS (Bacterial, Fungal and Parasitic)

Skin infections are typically classified into three main groups according to the type of organism responsible: bacterial, fungal, and parasitic. Below is a concise summary of each type.

Bacterial infections: Bacterial skin infections happen when pathogenic bacteria enter and grow in the skin. Typical conditions include impetigo, characterized by red blisters that rupture and develop yellow crusts; cellulitis, a deeper infection involving the skin and underlying tissues that leads to redness, swelling, and warmth; and folliculitis, which is inflammation of the hair follicles appearing as small red bumps or papules.

Fungal infections: Common fungal infections include athlete's foot (*Tinea pedis*), which impacts the feet and leads to itching, redness, and skin fissures; ringworm (*Tinea corporis*), recognized by round, red, scaly patches on the skin; jock itch (*Tinea cruris*), found in the groin area and characterized by itching, redness, and rash; and candidiasis, caused by *Candida* species, usually affecting warm, moist regions like the armpits and groin.

Parasitic infection: Microscopic mites that burrow into the skin cause scabies, a common parasitic skin condition that causes excruciating itching and a rash that resembles tiny papules. Pediculosis, or lice infestation, is the term for lice that dwell on the scalp, body, or pubic area and cause itching in addition to visible lice or eggs. Cutaneous larva migrans are painful, twisting trails left by certain parasite larvae that puncture the skin.

Hydrogel as Promising Topical Drug Delivery

Hydrogel formulations are a type of pharmaceutical dosage form designed for drug delivery in humans and animals. These hydrogels are water-containing materials capable of holding large quantities of water within their framework. The three-dimensional network structure of medicinal hydrogels often allows them to absorb and hold large volumes of water or other liquids, including medication solutions.^[22]

MOLECULAR STRUCTURE OF HYDROGELS

Hydrogels are three-dimensional (3D) networks of polymer chains that can absorb significant amounts of fluid due to hydrophilic functional groups like hydroxyl, carboxyl, amide, and amino groups connected to the polymer backbone. Van Bemmelen first used the term "hydrogel" in 1894. Hydrogels are physically and chemically crosslinked by hydrogen and

covalent bonds, and their molecular structure is determined by the size of their mesh. The main feature of hydrogels is their ability to hold significant amounts of water as water molecules penetrate and spread throughout the polymer network.

Crosslinking is essential to preserving the structural integrity of hydrogels, which are polymer networks that can deteriorate over time. By creating strong links between polymer chains, crosslinking produces a three-dimensional network structure. Hydrogels with three-dimensional structures that can hold a lot of water or biological fluids can be made from both synthetic and natural polymers. The choice of polymer is based on the intended characteristics and capabilities of the hydrogel, enabling fine tailoring to enhance biological performance and biocompatibility. When certain mechanical or chemical properties are needed for specific applications, synthetic hydrogels are frequently selected.

Because they are naturally biocompatible and biodegradable, natural polymers like chitosan and gelatin are frequently used in a variety of biomedical applications. The extracellular matrix can be replicated by natural hydrogels, creating an environment that promotes tissue regeneration and cell development. These materials are commonly used in tissue engineering, medication administration, and wound healing. The choice between natural and synthetic polymers for hydrogel formulation is influenced by a number of variables, including mechanical strength, rate of degradation, biocompatibility, and the specific requirements application. Both varieties have distinct advantages and can be modified to satisfy the particular needs of various industrial and biological procedures.

Figure No 2: Molecular Structure of Hydrogel.

Classification of hydrogel product based on sources

The origin or source, composition, structural qualities, type of crosslinking, network charge, stability, and reactivity to external stimuli are some of the criteria that can be used to categorize hydrogels.

The following are some typical categories.^[23]

Synthetic Source: Due to their water solubility, biocompatibility, and chemical inertness, synthetic polymers such as polyethylene glycol can be used in medical settings. Two or more hydroxyl groups in the linear and branched structures of polyethylene glycol (PEG) contribute to the crosslinking of hydrogels. Another hydrophilic synthetic polymer that is frequently utilized in the production of hydrogels is polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), which is transparent, sticky, and has a variety of mechanical qualities. For instance, a PVA-alginate hydrogel was created by Gulafshan et al. to accelerate wound healing. Polypropylene oxides, poloxamers, and poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) are further synthetic hydrogels.

Natural source: Polymers from marine, plant, and animal sources are used to create natural hydrogels. Chitosan, a naturally occurring mucoadhesive polysaccharide that is produced by deacetylating chitin, is one example. Because of its improved wound healing qualities and low toxicity, chitosan is frequently utilized in hydrogel synthesis. In this sense, Sheng et al. have reported its efficacy. Because of their low therapeutic toxicity and biodegradability, gelatin, collagen, cellulose, and alginate are other natural polymers that are utilized in hydrogels.

Product classification for hydrogel in light of crosslinking

Based on how they are prepared, crosslinked hydrogels are divided into two categories: chemically crosslinked and physically crosslinked. Compared to physical hydrogels, chemically crosslinked hydrogels create more durable and stable connections. These days, chemically crosslinked hydrogels are becoming more and more popular because of their exceptional mechanical strength.^[24]

Chemically Crosslinked Hydrogels: Because this type of polymer involves extensive crosslinking, it is favored over physical bonds. Ionic interactions, enzyme-catalysed reactions, and polymer-polymer conjugation are some of the mechanisms that bind crosslinking agents to the polymer backbone. A study described the use of free radical polymerization between β -cyclodextrin and favipiravir to create chemically crosslinked hydrogels for long-term drug release. Because of covalent bonding, these chemically crosslinked hydrogels have improved mechanical strength. Karoyo et al. reported using hexamethylene diisocyanate for chemical crosslinking to create a β -cyclodextrin hydrogel.

Physically Crosslinked Hydrogels: These hydrogels are put together physically by interactions between hydrogen bonds, electrostatic forces, and hydrophobic group particles. Using NaOH as the crosslinking agent, Gabriela et al. physically crosslinked chitosan to create porous hydrogels. Biocompatibility tests were carried out and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy was used to examine the physical characteristics. Curcumin has been used for generations as a natural treatment. It has anti-inflammatory qualities and regulates several transcription factors. This makes it potentially beneficial for treating chronic conditions such as neurodegenerative, cardiovascular, pulmonary, autoimmune, and neoplastic diseases, where inflammation is a key factor in disease development.

Technologies Adopted in hydrogel Preparation

Hydrogels are defined as polymer networks with hydrophilic characteristics. Although they are typically made from hydrophilic monomers, hydrophobic monomers may sometimes be incorporated to tailor properties for specific uses. Synthetic or natural polymers can be used to create hydrogels. Compared to natural polymers, synthetic polymers are stronger chemically because they are typically hydrophobic. Their enhanced mechanical strength leads to slower degradation but also increases durability, requiring a careful balance through optimal design. Natural polymer-based hydrogels can also be produced if the polymers possess appropriate functional groups or are modified with polymerizable groups. When polymer networks are crosslinked to produce an elastic structure, hydrogels are created. Hydrogels can be created using any technique that permits crosslinking of polymers. Frequently, hydrophilic monomers and multifunctional crosslinkers are combined in copolymerization or free-radical crosslinking polymerizations. Water-soluble linear polymers from both natural and synthetic sources are crosslinked by various means, including

- (1) Chemical reactions linking polymer chains,
- (2) Ionizing radiation that generates free radicals on polymer backbones which then form crosslinks, and
- (3) Physical interactions include crystallite formation, chain entanglements, and electrostatic forces.^[25]

Hydrogel technical features

- In saline solutions, equilibrium swelling is the maximum absorption capacity.
- Particle size and porosity have an impact on the desired absorption rate depending on the needs of the application

- Maximum absorbency under load, or absorbency under pressure (AUL)
- Most affordable price
- Exceptional stability and strength during storage and swelling
- High biodegradability without producing harmful byproducts as it breaks down
- Neutral pH following water swelling.
- It is absolutely non-toxic, colorless, and odorless.
- Stability against light exposure photostability.^[26]

Applications of hydrogels

Hydrogel patterns and shapes can be precisely designed using methods including photolithography, replica moulding, 3D bioprinting, direct-write assembly, microfluidics, and 3D sacrificial moulding, however the resolution that can be achieved is usually restricted to the micrometre or sub-micrometer scale. It is still quite difficult to create hydrogel patterns and arrays at the nanoscale, especially when making high-aspect-ratio hydrogel pillar arrays. Structural hydrogels have been widely explored for various applications including cell scaffolding, organ implantation, microfluidics, protein resistance, antifouling, lubrication, actuation, and drug delivery. Below, several key applications of structural hydrogels are highlighted, emphasizing the advantages of their unique morphologies.

Advantages of hydrogels

1. Offers high flexibility similar to that of natural tissues.
2. Biocompatible and biodegradable, allowing for injectable administration.
3. Delivers drugs locally, thus avoiding first-pass metabolism.
4. Provides sustained and prolonged drug release compared to traditional delivery systems.
5. Reduces the required dosage amount.
6. Minimizes side effects.
7. Enhances drug utilization efficiency.
8. Increases patient adherence to treatment.
9. Enables targeted drug delivery to specific sites, such as the colon.
10. Protects mucosal tissues from irritating drugs.
11. Prevents drug loss due to extensive first-pass metabolism.
12. Lowers the overall daily cost for patients by reducing the number of doses needed during treatment.^[27]

Figure No 3: Chemical Structure of Curcumin.^[28]

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF CURCUMIN

- Acts as an antioxidant
- Exhibits anti-inflammatory properties
- Provides cardioprotective effects
- Offers neuroprotective benefits
- Possesses anti-cancer activity
- Demonstrates antimicrobial effects.^[29]

Curcumin and its derivatives have been shown to have strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-infective, and antibacterial qualities. However, because of their hydrophobic nature, limited water solubility, low bioavailability, chemical instability, rapid metabolism, and short half-life, they pose serious challenges. effective and targeted distribution. To overcome these limitations, creative delivery methods have been developed. Nanoparticles, nanovesicles, polymeric micelles, hydrogels, nanofibers, nanohybrid scaffolds, and polymeric blend films have all greatly enhanced curcuminoids' aqueous solubility, oral bioavailability, stability, and enhancement of their antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory Curcumin derivatives are now more effective in both in vitro and in vivo experiments thanks to these developments in delivery technology.^[30]

The pilosebaceous follicles are affected by acne, of which acne vulgaris is the most common type. According to a Global Burden of condition research, 10% of people worldwide suffer from acne, making it the third most prevalent and eighth most common condition in the world. prevalent skin disorders.

Numerous psychological issues, such as anxiety, depression, suicidal thoughts, psychosomatic symptoms, social disengagement, and shame, have been connected to acne.^[31] Acne lesions are caused by four primary mechanisms: excessive sebum production by sebaceous glands, Cutibacterium acnes colonization of hair follicles, alterations in the keratinization process that lead to comedone formation, and the release of inflammatory

mediators on the skin. Clinical signs of acne include seborrhoea (excess fatty secretion), inflammatory lesions (pustules and papules), non-inflammatory lesions (open and closed comedones), post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, and varying.^[32]

Turmeric and curcumin's antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities have been investigated for their usefulness in treating acne. Both oral and topical turmeric formulations were assessed for the treatment of acne in a 2001 study by Lalla et al. Piper longum was used in the oral Curcuma longa pill. (black pepper) to improve the absorption of curcumin. Four groups were formed from a total of fifty-three participants:

1. Combining an active topical gel with an active oral tablet
2. Combining an active topical cream and an active oral tablet
3. Combining an active oral tablet with a topical version of a placebo
4. Oral placebo tablets and topical placebo formulations are combined.^[33]

APPLICATIONS OF CHITOSAN

Chitosan is widely valued for its versatility across various industries, including medicine, pharmaceuticals, food, cosmetics, agriculture, textiles, paper manufacturing, energy, and sustainable industrial practices. This reputation stems from its distinctive biological and physiological characteristics, such as solubility, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and chemical reactivity.

- Waste water treatment
 - Metal ion binding
 - Dye removal
 - Pesticide removal
- Food industry
 - Food additives
 - Antimicrobial agent
 - Emulsifier
 - Flocculant
- Agriculture
 - Controlled-release fertilizers
 - Enhancing water availability in plants
 - Protection against abiotic stress in crops
- Medical applications

- Drug delivery
- Wound dressings
- Dentistry
- Tissue engineering (chitosan membranes)

Cosmetics

- Sponges and sheets
- Hair serums
- Powders and pills
- Films and shampoos.^[34]

LIMITATIONS OF CHITOSAN

- Requires extensive purification to eliminate harmful substances.
- May contain contaminants such as proteins, metals, and toxins derived from shellfish.
- Exhibits poor water solubility at physiological pH levels.
- Shows instability in solutions, complicating its use in certain pharmaceuticals.
- Forms weak bonds with DNA/RNA, potentially impacting the effectiveness of gene therapy.
- Risks premature drug release, which can reduce therapeutic efficacy.
- Can trigger unexpected interactions when combined with other compounds.
- Its chemical properties limit its application in some medical treatments.^[35]

CATEGORIES OF CHITOSAN HYDROGEL

Physical and chemical hydrogels are the two forms of chitosan hydrogels that are distinguished by their network structure.

Physical chitosan hydrogels

Ionic linkages (ionically crosslinked hydrogels), secondary forces including hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals, and entanglements produced when chitosan dissolves in an acidic aqueous solution are some of the reversible interactions that result in the formation of physical chitosan hydrogels. Ionic interactions between chitosan and negatively charged polymers result in polyelectrolyte complexes, another type of physical chitosan hydrogel that usually has a high water content and electrical charge density. However, a significant drawback of hydrogels created by polyelectrolyte complexation is that the process must take place close to the pKa values of the involved polymers since both polymers must be ionized

with opposing charges. Consequently, controlling the pH during the process is crucial. Additionally, overly strong ionic interactions can lead to precipitation of the polyelectrolyte complex, necessitating careful monitoring throughout the reaction.

Hydrogels of chemical chitosan

By creating covalent connections through interchain interactions involving free amine groups from glucosamine units, chemical chitosan hydrogels are produced. In order to aid prevent or slow down dissolution and degradation, a crosslinking agent, such as glutaraldehyde, is usually added to the pre-hydrogel solution. The best method for increasing the hydrogel's wet strength is thought to be chemical crosslinking. Chemical hydrogels also have advantages over physical ones since the degree of crosslinking may be carefully adjusted to influence their features, such as gelation duration, mechanical strength, network pore size, degradation rate, swelling capacity, and drug release profile.^[36]

The creation and characteristics of hydrogels based on chitosan

Hydrogels based on chitosan (HGs) can be made from native chitosan alone, mixed with other polymers, or mixed with anionic small molecules. It is well known that chitosan dissolves in acidic environments when free amine groups (N-free) from glucosamine units are present. Because of their positive charge at acidic pH, these amine groups lessen interchain interactions. The ability to alter the apparent charge density by adjusting experimental factors including pH, ionic strength, and temperature has been used to create hydrogels. Chitosan can also self-crosslink by dissolving in a nonsolvent or raising the pH.

Chitosan can be combined with synthetic or natural polymers in a number of ways to acquire particular desired qualities. Typically, these techniques include:

- i) Chitosan's chemical crosslinking using crosslinking agents.
- ii) Chitosan chains are chemically modified to create macromonomers (crosslinkers).
- iii) Interactions that are hydrophobic,
- iv) Electrostatic forces, as well as
- v) Hydrogen connections. Hydrogel formation can also be facilitated by amine groups on chitosan forming hydrogen bonds with polymer chains.

Combining chitosan with other polymers offers the benefit of creating hybrid materials with unique characteristics. For instance, physically crosslinked chitosan hydrogels, which rely on non-covalent interactions, are naturally sensitive to external stimuli like pH and temperature

changes. Moreover, gelation can occur under mild conditions without needing crosslinking agents, enabling the encapsulation of proteins during the hydrogel synthesis process.^[37]

Figure No 4: Schematic Representation of the Treatment Procedure.^[33]

MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES

The phytoconstituents present in the CE were subjected to both qualitative and quantitative analysis. Following confirmation of the tests and method validation, a sustained-release hydrogel containing CE was developed. Additionally, the pharmacological properties of the enriched CE were evaluated using several in vitro assays.^[38]

Qualitative analysis of phytoconstituents

Alkaloids test

After adding a few drops of 1N hydrochloric acid (HCl), the extract was cooked for two to three minutes in a boiling water bath. It was filtered and combined with one or two drops of a 5% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution once it had cooled to room temperature. The emergence of a yellow precipitate or a cloudy yellow Alkaloids are present in the solution.

Test for glycosides

After treating the extract with NaOH, a few drops of 1N HCl were used to hydrolyze it. A crimson precipitate forms when a few drops of Fehling's solutions A and B are added to this mixture, verifying Glycosides are present.

Phenols test

After adding five milligrams of the extract to 0.5 milliliters of 20% sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), one or two drops of 1M NaOH. The presence of phenols is indicated by the development of a blue colour.

Test for tannins

A 5 mg of extract was mixed with 0.5 ml of a 5% ferric chloride ($FeCl_3$) solution. The development of a deep blue-black hue indicates that tannins are present.

Test for Flavonoids

NaOH test: A little amount of 1M NaOH and 1N HCl were added to around 1 ml of test solution. A yellowish-orange hue is indicative of flavonoids.

Sulfuric acid test: When concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) is added to one millilitre of test solution, an orange colour is produced, signifying the presence of flavonoids.

Saponins test

After adding a drop of sodium bicarbonate solution, the extract was given a good shake and allowed to stand for three minutes. The presence of saponins is confirmed by the creation of a persistent froth that resembles a honey comb when heated.

Carbohydrates test

Fehling's test: two millilitres of the test solution were combined with five millilitres of Fehling's solutions A and B. The mixture was then heated in a hot water bath for approximately five minutes. A yellow or red colour indicates carbohydrates.

Benedict's test: 2 ml of Benedict's reagent was combined with 1 ml of extract and heated in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes. The appearance of a reddish colour confirms carbohydrates.

Proteins test

Ninhydrin test: Ninhydrin solution dissolved in acetone was applied to the extract. The appearance of a purple hue indicates the presence of proteins.

Biuret test

Following preheating and filtration of the extract, it was treated with a 2% copper sulfate (CuSO_4) solution. The mixture was then combined with 95% ethanol and potassium hydroxide. Proteins are indicated by the development of a pinkish hue.

Estimation of total curcuminoids

Curcuminoid content was quantified utilizing an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity system and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). employing an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity system for High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). Using a Phenomenex Gemini C18 reversed-phase column, chromatographic separation was accomplished (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size). Acetonitrile and a 50 mM pH 3.5 potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer were combined in a 40:60 (v/v) ratio to form the mobile phase. The analysis was conducted during a 15-minute period at a flow rate of 0.8 ml/min and a column temperature of 25°C. UV absorption at 424 nm was used for detection after a 10 μl sample volume was injected.

Curcumin based hydrogel

Procedure for preparation:

A Remi Motor stirrer (Rajendra Elec. Ind. Ltd.) was used in the formulated formulation to dissolve 1.2% Sepimax ZenTM in the proper amount of distilled water. In the meantime, 0.5% Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) and 30 millilitres of 96% ethanol completely dissolved 1% CE. This CE solution was supplemented with 8% menthol, 4% propylene glycol (PG), and 3% isopropyl myristate (IPM). To create a 100 mg batch, the aqueous Sepimax ZenTM dispersion was gradually mixed with this CE combination. After gently stirring the mixture, it was allowed overnight to look for any phase separation. To neutralize the mixture and create a viscous hydrogel, triethanolamine (TEA) was then added dropwise. After bringing the pH down to 6.8, the finished hydrogel was kept in an incubator with temperature control for later usage.

Analysis of curcumin hydrogel**Measurement of pH**

A pH tester from Modern Scientific Company, India, was used to measure the pH. Three measurements were made, and the average result was noted.

Viscosity

A Brookfield viscometer (Model RVDV1+) was used to measure the hydrogel's viscosity. The mean viscosity was computed after measurements were made in triplicate.

Uniformity

After application, the produced hydrogel was visually assessed to determine how uniform its texture and look were. The ratings for homogeneity were +++ for good, ++ for fair, and + for bad.

Expandability

A glass slide with a diameter of 1 cm was covered with another identical slide after around 50 mg of gel had been uniformly applied to it. For 120 seconds, a 50 g weight was positioned on the upper slide without being move.

Moisture Content

Two grams of Curcuma longa hydrogel (CG) were placed in a desiccator containing anhydrous calcium chloride. The sample was weighed every 12 hours over three days or until weight remained constant. Moisture loss percentage was calculated using a standard formula.

Drug Content

50 millilitres of 96% ethanol were used to dissolve a 100 mg hydrogel sample. UV spectrophotometry at 426 nm was used to analyse the solution. A linear regression equation derived from a verified curcumin standard curve was used to determine the drug concentration.

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